

On Implicit Caputo Tempered Fractional Boundary Value Problems with Delay

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Abstract

This paper deals with some existence and uniqueness results for a class of problems for nonlinear Caputo tempered implicit fractional differential equations subject to boundary conditions and delay. The results are based on the fixed point theorems of Banach, Schauder and Schaefer. Furthermore, several illustrations are presented to demonstrate the plausibility of our results.

Keywords: Fixed point; implicit differential equations; existence; uniqueness; tempered fractional derivative; boundary condition.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, fractional calculus has shown to be a very useful tool for tackling the complexity structures seen in several disciplines of research. It is concerned with the extension of integer order differentiation and integration of a function to non-integer order, and its theory and application are substantial. We refer the reader to the monographs [1, 2, 25, 26] and the papers [22, 20, 13, 9, 16]. Many papers and monographs have lately been published in which the authors studied a wide range of results for various forms of differential equations, inclusions with different types of conditions. One may see the papers [1, 21, 6, 7], and the references therein.

Tempered fractional calculus can be considered as the extension of fractional calculus. Buschman's earlier work [8] was the first to disclose the definitions of fractional integration with weak singular and exponential kernels. See the papers [10, 23, 24, 19, 18, 17, 4] and references therein for more details and results on the

tempered fractional calculus.

Using Krasnoselskii fixed point theorem, Picard operator method and Gronwall’s inequality lemma, Almalahi *et al.* [3] considered the problem:

$$\begin{cases} {}^H D_{0^+}^{\zeta_1, \zeta_2; \psi} \chi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi(\theta), \chi(g(\theta))), & \theta \in (0, \varkappa) \\ I_{0^+}^{1-\zeta_3; \psi} \chi(0^+) = \sum_{j=1}^k c_j \chi(\tau_j), & \tau_j \in (0, \varkappa) \\ \chi(\theta) = \varphi(\theta), & \theta \in [-r, 0], \end{cases}$$

where ${}^H D_{0^+}^{\zeta_1, \zeta_2; \psi}(\cdot)$ is ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative operator of order $\zeta_1 \in (0, 1)$ and type $\zeta_2 \in [0, 1]$, $I_{0^+}^{1-\zeta_3; \psi}(\cdot)$ is ψ -fractional integral in Riemann-Liouville sense of order $1 - \zeta_3$; $\zeta_3 = \zeta_1 + \zeta_2(1 - \zeta_1)$, $0 < \zeta_3 < 1$, $\tau_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, k$, are prefixed points satisfying $0 < \tau_1 \leq \tau_2 \leq \dots \leq \tau_j < \varkappa$, and $c_j \in \mathbb{R}, \varphi \in C[-r, 0], \Psi : (0, \varkappa) \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a given continuous function, and $g : C(0, \varkappa) \rightarrow [-r, \varkappa]$ with $g(\theta) \leq \theta, r > 0$.

In [5], the authors considered the following fractional impulsive neutral integro-differential systems with infinite delay:

$$\begin{cases} D_{\theta}^q (\xi(\theta) - \chi(\theta, \xi_{\theta})) = A(\theta, \xi) (\xi(\theta) - \chi(\theta, \xi_{\theta})) + f\left(\theta, \xi_{\theta}, \int_0^{\theta} h(\theta, s, \xi_s) ds\right), \\ \theta \in [0, b], \quad \theta \neq \theta_k, \\ \Delta \xi|_{\theta=\theta_k} = I_k(\xi(\theta_k^-)), \quad \theta = \theta_k; k = 1, \dots, m, \\ \xi(0) + g(\xi) = \phi, \quad \phi \in B_{\vartheta}, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < q < 1$, D_{θ}^q is the Caputo fractional derivative and Let $\xi_{\theta}(\cdot)$ denote $\xi_{\theta}(\theta) = \xi(\theta + \theta), \theta \in (-\infty, 0]$. The results are obtained by a fixed point theorem.

In [15], the authors discussed the existence of solutions for the following initial value problem of conformable implicit impulsive fractional differential equations with infinite delay:

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{T}_{\theta_j}^r \chi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_{\theta}, \mathcal{T}_j^r \chi(\theta)), & \theta \in \Theta_j; j = 0, 1, \dots, \mathfrak{T}, \\ \Delta \chi|_{\theta=\theta_j} = \mathfrak{h}_j(\chi_{\theta_j^-}), & j = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{T}, \\ \chi(\theta) = \wp(\theta), & \theta \in (-\infty, a], \end{cases}$$

where $0 \leq a = \theta_0 < \theta_1 < \dots < \theta_{\mathfrak{T}} < \theta_{\mathfrak{T}+1} = \beta < \infty$, $\mathcal{T}_{\theta_j}^r \chi(\theta)$ is the conformable fractional derivative of order $r \in (0, 1)$, $\Psi : \Theta \times \mathcal{G} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a given continuous function, $\Theta := [a, \beta]$, $\Theta_0 := [a, \theta_1]$, $\Theta_j := (\theta_j, \theta_{j+1}]; j = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{T}$, $\wp : (-\infty, a] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathfrak{h}_j : \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given continuous functions, \mathcal{G} is called a phase space.

In this paper, first we investigate the following class of Caputo tempered fractional differential equation with finite delay:

$$\begin{cases} \left({}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \chi \right) (\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_{\theta}, \mathfrak{D}_0^{\zeta} \chi(\theta)); & \theta \in \Theta := [0, \varpi], \\ \chi(\theta) = \wp(\theta), & \theta \in [-\kappa, 0], \\ \iota \chi(0) + j \chi(\varpi) = \varrho, \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

where $0 < \zeta < 1, \varepsilon \geq 0, {}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon}$ is the Caputo tempered fractional derivative, $\Psi : \Theta \times C([-\kappa, 0], \mathbb{R}) \times \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function, $\wp \in C([-\kappa, \varpi], \mathbb{R}), 0 < \varpi < +\infty, \iota, j, \varrho$ are real constants, and $\kappa > 0$ is the time delay. For any $\theta \in \Theta$, we give χ_{θ} by

$$\chi_{\theta}(\vartheta) = \chi(\theta + \vartheta); \text{ for } \vartheta \in [-\kappa, 0].$$

Next, we consider the following infinite delay problem:

$$\begin{cases} \left({}_0^C \mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \chi \right) (\theta) = \Psi \left(\theta, \chi_\theta, \mathfrak{D}_0^\zeta \chi(\theta) \right); \theta \in \Theta \\ \chi(\theta) = \wp(\theta), \theta \in (-\infty, 0], \\ \iota \chi(0) + J\chi(\varpi) = \varrho, \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

where $\Psi : \Theta \times \mathcal{G} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\wp : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given continuous functions, and \mathcal{G} is called a phase space that will be determined later. For any $\theta \in \Theta$, we define $\chi_\theta \in \mathcal{G}$ by

$$\chi_\theta(\vartheta) = \chi(\theta + \vartheta); \text{ for } \vartheta \in (-\infty, 0].$$

In the next segment, we look into the following state-dependent finite delay problem:

$$\begin{cases} \left({}_0^C \mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \chi \right) (\theta) = \Psi \left(\theta, \chi_{\rho(\theta, \chi_\theta)}, \mathfrak{D}_0^\zeta \chi(\theta) \right); \theta \in \Theta, \\ \chi(\theta) = \wp(\theta), \theta \in [-\kappa, 0], \\ \iota \chi(0) + J\chi(\varpi) = \varrho, \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

where $\Psi \in C((0, \varpi], \mathbb{R})$, $\rho : \Theta \times C([-\kappa, \varpi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\wp \in C([-\kappa, \varpi], \mathbb{R})$ are given continuous functions.

Finally, we study the following problem with state dependent infinite delay:

$$\begin{cases} \left({}_0^C \mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \chi \right) (\theta) = \Psi \left(\theta, \chi_{\rho(\theta, \chi_\theta)}, \mathfrak{D}_0^\zeta \chi(\theta) \right); \theta \in \Theta, \\ \chi(\theta) = \wp(\theta), \theta \in (-\infty, 0], \\ \iota \chi(0) + J\chi(\varpi) = \varrho, \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

where $\Psi : \Theta \times \mathcal{G} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\wp : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given continuous functions.

2. Preliminaries

First, we give the definitions and the notations that we will use throughout this paper. We denote by $C(\Theta, \mathbb{R})$ the Banach space of all continuous functions from Θ and $[-\kappa, 0]$ into \mathbb{R} respectively, with the following norms

$$\|\chi\|_\infty = \sup_{\theta \in \Theta} \{|\chi(\theta)|\}$$

and

$$\|\chi\|_{[-\kappa, 0]} = \sup_{\theta \in [-\kappa, 0]} \{|\chi(\theta)|\}.$$

Let $\mathcal{C} := C([-\kappa, \varpi])$ be a Banach space with the norm

$$\|\chi\|_{\mathcal{C}} := \sup_{\theta \in [-\kappa, \varpi]} |\chi(\theta)|.$$

As usual, $AC(\Theta)$ denotes the space of absolutely continuous functions from Θ into \mathbb{R} . For any $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, we denote by $AC^n(\Theta)$ the space defined by

$$AC^n(\Theta) := \left\{ \Psi : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : \frac{d^n}{d\theta^n} \Psi(\theta) \in AC(\Theta) \right\}.$$

Consider the space $X_b^p(\kappa_1, \kappa_2)$, ($b \in E$, $1 \leq p \leq \infty$) of those complex-valued Lebesgue measurable functions f on $[\kappa_1, \kappa_2]$ for which $\|\Psi\|_{X_b^p} < \infty$, where the norm is defined by:

$$\|\Psi\|_{X_b^p} = \left(\int_{\kappa_1}^{\kappa_2} |\theta^b \Psi(\theta)|^p \frac{d\theta}{\theta} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad (1 \leq p < \infty, b \in \mathbb{R}).$$

Definition 2.1 (The Riemann-Liouville tempered fractional integral [10, 23, 24]). *Suppose that the real function f is piecewise continuous on $[\kappa_1, \kappa_2]$ and $f \in X_b^p(\kappa_1, \kappa_2)$, $\varepsilon > 0$. Then, the Riemann-Liouville tempered fractional integral of order ζ is defined by*

$${}_{\kappa_1}I_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \Psi(\theta) = e^{-\varepsilon\theta} {}_{\kappa_1}I_{\theta}^{\zeta} \left(e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta) \right) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_{\kappa_1}^{\theta} \frac{e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} \Psi(\lambda)}{(\theta-\lambda)^{1-\zeta}} d\lambda, \tag{5}$$

where ${}_{\kappa_1}I_{\theta}^{\zeta}$ denotes the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral [14], defined by

$${}_{\kappa_1}I_{\theta}^{\zeta} \Psi(\theta) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_{\kappa_1}^{\theta} \frac{\Psi(\lambda)}{(\theta-\lambda)^{1-\zeta}} d\lambda. \tag{6}$$

Obviously, the tempered fractional integral (5) reduces to the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral (6) if $\varepsilon = 0$.

Definition 2.2 (The Riemann-Liouville tempered fractional derivative [10, 23]). *For $n-1 < \zeta < n$; $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $\varepsilon \geq 0$. The Riemann-Liouville tempered fractional derivative is defined by*

$${}_{\kappa_1}\mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \Psi(\theta) = e^{-\varepsilon\theta} {}_{\kappa_1}\mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} \left(e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta) \right) = \frac{e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(n-\zeta)} \frac{d^n}{d\theta^n} \int_{\kappa_1}^{\theta} \frac{e^{\varepsilon\lambda} f(\lambda)}{(\theta-\lambda)^{\zeta-n+1}} d\theta,$$

where ${}_{\kappa_1}\mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} (e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta))$ denotes the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative [14], given by

$${}_{\kappa_1}\mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} \left(e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta) \right) = \frac{d^n}{d\theta^n} \left({}_{\kappa_1}I_{\theta}^{n-\zeta} \left(e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta) \right) \right) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\zeta)} \frac{d^n}{d\theta^n} \int_{\kappa_1}^{\theta} \frac{(e^{\varepsilon\lambda} \Psi(\lambda))}{(\theta-\lambda)^{\zeta-n+1}} d\lambda.$$

Definition 2.3 (The Caputo tempered fractional derivative [10, 24]). *For $n-1 < \zeta < n$; $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $\varepsilon \geq 0$. The Caputo tempered fractional derivative is defined as*

$${}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \Psi(\theta) = e^{-\varepsilon\theta} {}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} \left(e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta) \right) = \frac{e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(n-\zeta)} \int_{\kappa_1}^{\theta} \frac{1}{(\theta-\lambda)^{\zeta-n+1}} \frac{d^n (e^{\varepsilon\lambda} \Psi(\lambda))}{d\lambda^n} d\lambda,$$

where ${}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} (e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta))$ denotes the Caputo fractional derivative [14], given by

$${}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} \left(e^{\varepsilon\theta} \Psi(\theta) \right) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\zeta)} \int_{\kappa_1}^{\theta} \frac{1}{(\theta-\lambda)^{\zeta-n+1}} \frac{d^n (e^{\varepsilon\lambda} \Psi(\lambda))}{d\lambda^n} d\lambda.$$

Lemma 2.4 ([10]). *For a constant C ,*

$${}_{\kappa_1}\mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} C = C e^{-\varepsilon\theta} {}_{\kappa_1}\mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} e^{\varepsilon\theta}, \quad {}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} C = C e^{-\varepsilon\theta} {}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} e^{\varepsilon\theta}.$$

Obviously, ${}_{\kappa_1}\mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} (C) \neq {}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} (C)$. And, ${}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} (C)$ is no longer equal to zero, being different from ${}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta} (C) \equiv 0$.

Lemma 2.5 ([10, 24]). *Let $f(\theta) \in AC^n[\kappa_1, \kappa_2]$, $\varepsilon \geq 0$ and $n-1 < \zeta < n$. Then the Caputo tempered fractional derivative and the Riemann-Liouville tempered fractional integral have the following composite properties:*

$${}_{\kappa_1}I_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \left[{}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} f(\theta) \right] = f(\theta) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \frac{(\theta-\kappa_1)^k}{k!} \left[\frac{d^k (e^{\varepsilon\theta} f(\theta))}{d\theta^k} \Bigg|_{\theta=\kappa_1} \right],$$

and

$${}_{\kappa_1}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} \left[{}_{\kappa_1}I_{\theta}^{\zeta, \varepsilon} f(\theta) \right] = f(\theta), \text{ for } \zeta \in (0, 1).$$

Lemma 2.6. *Let $\Phi \in L^1(\Theta)$ and $0 < \zeta \leq 1$. Then the boundary value problem*

$$\begin{cases} \left({}_0^C \mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\zeta, \varepsilon} y\right) (\theta) = \Phi(\theta); \theta \in \Theta := [0, \varpi], \\ \iota \chi(0) + j \chi(\varpi) = \varrho, \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

has a unique solution defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(\theta) = & \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon \theta}}{\iota e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon \theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\iota e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Proof. Applying the Riemann-Liouville tempered fractional integral of order ζ to both sides the equation

$$\left({}_0^C \mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\zeta, \varepsilon} y\right) (\theta) = \Phi(\theta),$$

and by using Lemma 2.5 and if $\theta \in \Theta$, we get

$$\chi(\theta) - \chi(0)e^{-\varepsilon \theta} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda.$$

Hence, we get

$$\chi(\theta) = \chi(0)e^{-\varepsilon \theta} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda.$$

Thus,

$$\chi(\varpi) = \chi(0)e^{-\varepsilon \varpi} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda.$$

From the mixed boundary conditions $\iota \chi(0) + j \chi(\varpi) = \varrho$, we get

$$\iota \chi(0) + j \left(\chi(0)e^{-\varepsilon \varpi} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right) = \varrho.$$

Thus,

$$\chi(0) = \frac{\varrho - \frac{j}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda}{\iota + j e^{-\varepsilon \varpi}}.$$

Hence, we obtain (8).

Conversely, we can easily show by Lemma 2.4 and Lemma 2.5 that if χ verifies equation (8), then it satisfied the problem (7). □

3. Existence Results for the First Problem

Definition 3.1. *A solution of problem (1) is a function $\chi \in C([-\kappa, \varpi], \mathbb{R})$ where*

$$\chi(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon \theta}}{\iota e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon \theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\iota e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda, \theta \in [0, \varpi], \\ \wp(\theta), \theta \in [-\kappa, 0], \end{cases}$$

such that $\Phi \in C(\Theta)$, with $\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_\theta, \Phi(\theta))$.

The hypotheses:

- (H_1) There exist constantes $\omega_1 > 0$, $0 < \omega_2 < 1$ such that:

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) - \Psi(\theta, \chi_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)| \leq \omega_1 \|\chi_1 - \chi_2\|_{[-\kappa, 0]} + \omega_2 |\mathfrak{S}_1 - \mathfrak{S}_2|,$$

for any $\chi_1, \chi_2 \in C([-\kappa, 0], \mathbb{R})$, $\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, and each $\theta \in \Theta$.

Remark 3.2. We note that by taking:

$$\varpi_1 = \omega_1, \quad \varpi_2 = \omega_2, \quad \text{and } \varpi_3 = \Psi^*,$$

where $\Psi^* = \sup_{\theta \in [0, \varpi]} \Psi(\theta, 0, 0)$. Then, hypothesis (H_1) implies that

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S})| \leq \varpi_1 \|\chi\|_{[-\kappa, 0]} + \varpi_2 |\mathfrak{S}| + \varpi_3.$$

Now, we will give our first existence and uniqueness result that is based on Banach’s fixed point theorem [11].

Theorem 3.3. Assume that the hypothesis (H_1) holds. If

$$\ell := \frac{\varpi^\zeta (\nu e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + 2j)\omega_1}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\nu e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j)(1 - \omega_2)} < 1, \tag{9}$$

then problem (1) has a unique solution on $[-\kappa, \varpi]$.

Proof. Consider the operator $\mathcal{H} : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ such that,

$$(\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{\rho e^{-\varepsilon \theta}}{\nu e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon \theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\nu e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda, \quad \theta \in [0, \varpi], \\ \wp(\theta), \quad \theta \in [-\kappa, 0], \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

where $\Phi \in C(\Theta)$, with $\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_\theta, \Phi(\theta))$.

Let $\chi, \mathfrak{S} \in C(\Theta)$. Then, for each $\theta \in [-\kappa, 0]$, we get

$$|(\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta) - (\mathcal{H}\mathfrak{S})(\theta)| = 0,$$

and for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |(\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta) - (\mathcal{H}\mathfrak{S})(\theta)| &\leq \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon \theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\nu e^{\varepsilon \varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda) - \Upsilon(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda) - \Upsilon(\lambda)| d\lambda, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi, \Upsilon \in C(\Theta)$ such that

$$\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Upsilon(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \mathfrak{S}_\theta, \Upsilon(\theta)).$$

From (H_1) , we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi(\theta) - \Upsilon(\theta)| &= |\Psi(\theta, \chi_\theta, \Phi(\theta)) - \Psi(\theta, \mathfrak{S}_\theta, \Upsilon(\theta))| \\ &\leq \omega_1 \|\chi_\theta - \mathfrak{S}_\theta\|_{[-\kappa, 0]} + \omega_2 |\Phi(\theta) - \Upsilon(\theta)|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\|\Phi - \Upsilon\|_\infty \leq \frac{\omega_1}{1 - \omega_2} \|\chi - \mathfrak{S}\|_C.$$

Then, for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} |(\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta) - (\mathcal{H}\mathfrak{S})(\theta)| &\leq \frac{\varpi^\zeta(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)\omega_1}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - \omega_2)} \|\chi - \mathfrak{S}\|_C \\ &\leq \ell \|\chi - \mathfrak{S}\|_C. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we get

$$\|\mathcal{H}\chi - \mathcal{H}\mathfrak{S}\|_C \leq \ell \|\chi - \mathfrak{S}\|_C.$$

Consequently, by Banach’s fixed point theorem, the operator \mathcal{H} has a unique fixed point, which is the unique solution of our problem (1) on $[-\kappa, \varpi]$. \square

Theorem 3.4. *If (H_1) holds, and*

$$\frac{\varpi^\zeta(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)\varpi_1}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - \varpi_2)} < 1,$$

then problem (1) has at least one solution on $[-\kappa, \varpi]$.

Proof. Consider the operator \mathcal{H} defined in (10). Let $\delta > 0$ such that

$$\delta \geq \max \left\{ \|\wp\|_{[-\kappa, 0]}, \frac{\frac{\varrho}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} + \frac{\varpi^\zeta(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)\varpi_3}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - \varpi_2)}}{1 - \frac{\varpi^\zeta(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)\varpi_1}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - \varpi_2)}} \right\}. \tag{11}$$

Consider the ball

$$\Xi_\delta = \{\xi \in C([-\kappa, \varpi], \mathbb{R}), \|\xi\|_C \leq \delta\}.$$

Claim 1. \mathcal{H} is continuous.

Let $\{\chi_n\}_n$ be a sequence such that $\chi_n \rightarrow \chi$ on Ξ_δ . For each $\theta \in [-\kappa, 0]$, we have

$$|(\mathcal{H}\chi_n)(\theta) - (\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta)| = 0,$$

and for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |(\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta) - (\mathcal{H}\mathfrak{S})(\theta)| &\leq \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi - \lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta - 1)} |\Phi_n(\lambda) - \Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta - \lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta - 1)} |\Phi_n(\lambda) - \Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi_n, \Phi \in C(\Theta, \mathbb{R})$ such that

$$\Phi_n(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_{nt}, \Phi_n(\theta)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_\theta, \Phi(\theta)).$$

Since

$$\|\chi_n - \chi\|_C \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

and Ψ, Φ and Φ_n are continuous, we deduce that

$$\|\mathcal{H}(\chi_n) - \mathcal{H}(\chi)\|_C \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence, \mathcal{H} is continuous.

Claim 2. $\mathcal{H}(\Xi_\delta) \subset \Xi_\delta$.

Let $\chi \in \Xi_\delta$, If $\theta \in [-\kappa, 0]$ then $\|(\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta)\| \leq \|\varphi\|_C \leq \delta$. From Remark 3.2, for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi(\theta)| &\leq |\Psi(\theta, \chi_\theta, \Phi(\theta))| \\ &\leq \varpi_1 \|\chi_\theta\|_{[-\kappa, 0]} + \varpi_2 |\Phi(\theta)| + \varpi_3 \\ &\leq \varpi_1 \|\chi\|_C + \varpi_2 \|\Phi\|_\infty + \varpi_3 \\ &\leq \varpi_1 \delta + \varpi_2 \|\Phi\|_\infty + \varpi_3. \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\|\Phi\|_\infty \leq \frac{\delta\varpi_1 + \varpi_3}{1 - \varpi_2}.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} |(\mathcal{H}\chi)(\theta)| &\leq \left| \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} + \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &\leq \frac{\varrho}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} + \frac{\varpi^\zeta (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j) (\delta\varpi_1 + \varpi_3)}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1) (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j) (1 - \varpi_2)} \\ &\leq \delta. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|\mathcal{H}(\chi)\|_C \leq \delta.$$

Consequently, $\mathcal{H}(\Xi_\delta) \subset \Xi_\delta$.

Claim 3. $\mathcal{H}(\Xi_\delta)$ is equicontinuous.

For $0 \leq \theta_1 \leq \theta_2 \leq \varpi$, and $\chi \in \Xi_\delta$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_1) - \mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_2)| &\leq \left| \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right. \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta_1} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta_1-\lambda)} (\theta_1 - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ &\quad - \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} + \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta_2} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta_2-\lambda)} (\theta_2 - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\varrho (e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1} - e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2})}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} + \frac{\varpi^\zeta j (\delta\varpi_1 + \varpi_3) (e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1} - e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2})}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1) (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j) (1 - \varpi_2)} \\ &\quad + \frac{(\delta\varpi_1 + \varpi_3) [(\theta_2 - \theta_1)^\zeta + \theta_2^\zeta - \theta_1^\zeta]}{(1 - \varpi_2) \Gamma(\zeta + 1)}. \end{aligned}$$

As $\theta_2 \rightarrow \theta_1$ then $|\mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_1) - \mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_2)| \rightarrow 0$. We deduce that $\mathcal{H}(\Xi_\delta)$ is equicontinuous.

Consequently, Arzelá-Ascoli theorem implies that \mathcal{H} is continuous and compact. Thus, by Schauder's fixed point theorem [11], we deduce that \mathcal{H} has at least a fixed point which is a solution of (1). \square

4. Existence Results for the Second Problem

In this section, we are concerned with the existence results of (2). Let the space $(\mathcal{G}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is a seminormed linear space of functions mapping $(-\infty, 0]$ into \mathbb{R} , and verifying the following axioms which were derived from Hale and Kato’s originals [12]:

(Ax₁) If $\chi : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and $\chi_0 \in \mathcal{G}$, then there exist constants $\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3 > 0$, such that for each $\theta \in \Theta$; we have:

- (i) χ_{θ} is in \mathcal{G} ,
- (ii) $\|\chi_{\theta}\|_{\mathcal{G}} \leq \xi_1 \|\chi_1\|_{\mathcal{G}} + \xi_2 \sup_{\vartheta \in [0, \theta]} |\chi(\vartheta)|$,
- (iii) $\|\chi(\theta)\| \leq \xi_3 \|\chi_{\theta}\|_{\mathcal{G}}$.

(Ax₂) For the function $\chi(\cdot)$ in (Ax₁), χ_{θ} is a \mathcal{G} - valued continuous function on Θ .

(Ax₃) The space \mathcal{G} is complete.

Consider the space

$$\Xi = \{\chi : (-\infty, \varpi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \chi|_{(-\infty, 0]} \in \mathcal{G}, \chi|_{\Theta} \in C([-\kappa, \varpi], \mathbb{R})\}.$$

Definition 4.1. By a solution of problem (2), we mean a function $\chi \in \Xi$ such that

$$\chi(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^{\varpi} e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda, \theta \in [0, \varpi], \\ \varphi(\theta), \theta \in [-\infty, 0], \end{cases}$$

where $\Phi \in C(\Theta)$, with $\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_{\theta}, \Phi(\theta))$.

The hypothesis:

- (H₂) The function Ψ verifies:

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) - \Psi(\theta, \chi_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)| \leq b_1 \|\chi_1 - \chi_2\|_{\mathcal{G}} + b_2 |\mathfrak{S}_1 - \mathfrak{S}_2|,$$

for any $\chi_1, \mathfrak{S}_1 \in \mathcal{G}$, $\chi_2, \mathfrak{S}_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, and each $\theta \in \Theta$, where $b_1 > 0$ and $0 < b_2 < 1$.

Remark 4.2. We note that by taking:

$$B_1 = b_1, \quad B_2 = b_2, \quad \text{and } B_3 = \Psi^*,$$

where $\Psi^* = \sup_{\theta \in [0, \varpi]} \Psi(\theta, 0, 0)$. Then, hypothesis (H₂) implies that

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S})| \leq B_1 \|\chi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_2 |\mathfrak{S}| + B_3,$$

for any $\chi \in \mathcal{G}$, $\mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{R}$, and each $\theta \in \Theta$.

Theorem 4.3. Suppose that (H₂) is verified. If

$$\bar{\varepsilon} := \frac{\varpi^{\zeta}(\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)b_1}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - b_2)} < 1, \tag{12}$$

then (2) admit a unique solution on $(-\infty, \varpi]$.

Proof. Define the operator $N_1 : \Xi \rightarrow \Xi$ where,

$$(N_1\chi)(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda, & \theta \in [0, \varpi], \\ \wp(\theta), & \theta \in [-\infty, 0], \end{cases}$$

where $\Phi \in C(\Theta)$, with $\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_\theta, \Phi(\theta))$.

Let $\varkappa_1 : (-\infty, \varpi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function given by

$$\varkappa_1(\theta) = \begin{cases} \wp(\theta); & \theta \in (-\infty, 0], \\ \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi}}; & \theta \in \Theta. \end{cases}$$

Then $\varkappa_{10} = \wp$. For each $\varkappa_2 \in C(\Theta)$, with $\varkappa_2(0) = 0$, we denote by $\overline{\varkappa_2}$ the function defined by

$$\overline{\varkappa_2} = \begin{cases} 0, & \theta \in (-\infty, 0], \\ \varkappa_2(\theta), & \theta \in \Theta. \end{cases}$$

If $\chi(\cdot)$ satisfies the integral equation

$$\chi(\theta) = \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda,$$

we can decompose $\chi(\cdot)$ as $\chi(\theta) = \overline{\varkappa_2}(\theta) + \varkappa_1(\theta)$; for $\theta \in \Theta$, which implies that $\chi_\theta = \overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}$ for every $\theta \in \Theta$, and the function $\varkappa_2(\cdot)$ satisfies

$$\varkappa_2(\theta) = -\frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda,$$

where

$$\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Phi(\theta)); \theta \in \Theta.$$

Set

$$\mathcal{D}_0 = \{\varkappa_2 \in C(\Theta); \varkappa_{20} = 0\},$$

and let $\|\cdot\|_\varpi$ be the norm in \mathcal{D}_0 defined by

$$\|\varkappa_2\|_\varpi = \|\varkappa_{20}\|_{\mathcal{G}} + \sup_{\theta \in \Theta} |\varkappa_2(\theta)| = \sup_{\theta \in \Theta} |\varkappa_2(\theta)|; \varkappa_2 \in \mathcal{D}_0,$$

where \mathcal{D}_0 is a Banach space with norm $\|\cdot\|_T$. Define the operator $\mathcal{K} : \mathcal{D}_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_0$ by

$$(\mathcal{K}\varkappa_2)(\theta) = -\frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda, \tag{13}$$

where

$$\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Phi(\theta)); \theta \in \Theta.$$

We shall show that $\mathcal{K} : \mathcal{D}_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_0$ is a contraction map. Let $\varkappa_2, \varkappa_2' \in \mathcal{D}_0$, then we have for each $\theta \in \Theta$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2)(\theta) - \mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2')(\theta)| &\leq \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda) - \Upsilon(\lambda)| d\lambda \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda) - \Upsilon(\lambda)| d\lambda,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{14}$$

where $\Phi, \Upsilon \in C(\Theta)$ such that

$$\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Phi(\theta)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Upsilon(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa_2'}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Upsilon(\theta)).$$

Since, for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we have

$$|\Phi(\theta) - \Upsilon(\theta)| \leq \frac{b_1}{1 - b_2} \|\overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta - \overline{\varkappa_2'}_\theta\|_{\mathcal{G}}.$$

Then, for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2)(\theta) - \mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2')(\theta)| &\leq \frac{b_1}{(1-b_2)} \|\overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta - \overline{\varkappa_2'}_\theta\|_{\mathcal{G}} \\
 &\leq \frac{\varpi^\zeta (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j) b_1}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1) (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j) (1 - b_2)} \|\overline{\varkappa_2} - \overline{\varkappa_2'}\|_{\varpi} \\
 &= \bar{\varepsilon} \|\overline{\varkappa_2} - \overline{\varkappa_2'}\|_{\varpi}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we get

$$\|\mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2) - \mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2')\|_{\varpi} \leq \bar{\varepsilon} \|\overline{\varkappa_2} - \overline{\varkappa_2'}\|_{\varpi}.$$

Hence, from the Banach contraction principle, \mathcal{K} has a unique fixed point. Thus, the existence of the unique solution of problem (2). □

Theorem 4.4. *Suppose that (H_2) is verified. Then (2) admit at least one solution on $(-\infty, \varpi]$.*

Proof. Consider $\mathcal{K} : \mathcal{D}_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_0$ given in (13), For $\delta > 0$, let

$$\Xi_\delta = \{\varkappa_1 \in \mathcal{D}_0, \|\varkappa_1\|_{\varpi} \leq \delta\}.$$

Claim 1. \mathcal{H} is continuous.

Let \varkappa_{2n} be a sequence where $\varkappa_{2n} \rightarrow \varkappa_2$ in \mathcal{D}_0 . For $\theta \in \Theta$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 |(\mathcal{K}\varkappa_{2n})(\theta) - (\mathcal{K}\varkappa_2)(\theta)| &\leq \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi_n(\lambda) - \Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi_n(\lambda) - \Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{15}$$

where $\Phi_n, \Phi \in C(\Theta)$ such that

$$\Phi_n(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa_{2n}}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Phi_n(\theta)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Phi(\theta)).$$

Since $\|\varkappa_{2n} - \varkappa_2\|_{\varpi} \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and Ψ, Φ and Φ_n are continuous, then

$$\|\mathcal{K}(\varkappa_n) - \mathcal{K}(\varkappa)\|_{\varpi} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence, \mathcal{K} is continuous.

Claim 2. $\mathcal{K}(\Xi_\delta)$ is bounded.

Let $\varkappa_2 \in \Xi_\delta$, for $\theta \in \Theta$, we obtain

$$|\Phi(\theta)| \leq |\Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa_2}_\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Phi(\theta))|$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq B_1 \|\overline{\varkappa}_2\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_2 |\Phi(\theta)| + B_3 \\ &\leq B_1 [\|\overline{\varkappa}_2\theta\|_{\mathcal{G}} + \|\varkappa_{1\theta}\|_{\mathcal{G}}] + B_2 \|\Phi\|_{\infty} + B_3 \\ &\leq B_1 \xi_2 \delta + B_1 \xi_1 \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_2 \|\Phi\|_{\infty} + B_3. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\|\Phi\|_{\infty} \leq \frac{B_1 \xi_2 \delta + B_1 \xi_1 \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_3}{1 - B_2}.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} |(\mathcal{K}\varkappa_2)(\theta)| &\leq \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^{\varpi} e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &\leq \frac{\varpi^{\zeta} (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j) (B_1 \xi_2 \delta + B_1 \xi_1 \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_3)}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1) (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j) (1 - B_2)} \\ &:= \tilde{\ell}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|\mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2)\|_{\varpi} \leq \tilde{\ell}.$$

Claim 3. $\mathcal{K}(\Xi_{\delta})$ is equicontinuous.

For $0 \leq \theta_1 \leq \theta_2 \leq \varpi$, and $\varkappa_2 \in \Xi_{\delta}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_1) - \mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_2)| &\leq \left| \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^{\varpi} e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right. \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta_1} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta_1-\lambda)} (\theta_1 - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ &\quad - \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} + \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^{\varpi} e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta_2} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta_2-\lambda)} (\theta_2 - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\varrho (e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1} - e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2})}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} + \frac{\varpi^{\zeta} j (B_1 \xi_2 \delta + B_1 \xi_1 \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_3) (e^{-\varepsilon\theta_1} - e^{-\varepsilon\theta_2})}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1) (\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j) (1 - B_2)} \\ &\quad + \frac{(B_1 \xi_2 \delta + B_1 \xi_1 \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_3) [(\theta_2 - \theta_1)^{\zeta} + \theta_2^{\zeta} - \theta_1^{\zeta}]}{(1 - B_2) \Gamma(\zeta + 1)}. \end{aligned}$$

As $\theta_2 \rightarrow \theta_1$ then $|\mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_1) - \mathcal{H}(\chi)(\theta_2)| \rightarrow 0$. Thus, $\mathcal{K} : \mathcal{D}_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_0$ is completely continuous.

Claim 4. The priori bounds.

We prove that the set

$$\mathcal{E} = \{\chi \in \mathcal{D}_0 : \chi = \tilde{\varepsilon} \mathcal{K}(\chi); \text{ for some } \tilde{\varepsilon} \in (0, 1)\}$$

is bounded. Let $\varkappa_2 \in \mathcal{D}_0$. Let $u \in \mathcal{D}_0$, such that $\varkappa_2 = \tilde{\varepsilon} \mathcal{K}(\varkappa_2)$; for some $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$. Then for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varkappa_2(\theta) = \tilde{\varepsilon} (\mathcal{K}\varkappa_2)(\theta) = \tilde{\varepsilon} &\left(-\frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^{\varpi} e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \right). \end{aligned}$$

By Remark 4.2 we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi(\theta)| &\leq |\Psi(\theta, \overline{\varkappa}_2\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}, \Phi(\theta))| \\ &\leq B_1\|\overline{\varkappa}_2\theta + \varkappa_{1\theta}\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_2|\Phi(\theta)| + B_3 \\ &\leq B_1[\|\overline{\varkappa}_2\theta\|_{\mathcal{G}} + \|\varkappa_{1\theta}\|_{\mathcal{G}}] + B_2\|\Phi\|_{\infty} + B_3 \\ &\leq B_1\xi_2\|\varkappa_2\|_{\varpi} + B_1\xi_1\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_2\|\Phi\|_{\infty} + B_3. \end{aligned}$$

This gives,

$$\|\Phi\|_{\infty} \leq \frac{B_1\xi_2\|\varkappa_2\|_{\varpi} + B_1\xi_1\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_3}{1 - B_2} := \eta.$$

Thus, for each $\theta \in \Theta$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\varkappa_2(\theta)| &\leq \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^{\varpi} e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} |\Phi(\lambda)| d\lambda \\ &\leq \frac{\varpi^{\zeta}(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)\eta}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \\ &:= \eta'. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|\varkappa_2\|_{\varpi} \leq \eta'.$$

This shows that the set \mathcal{E} is bounded. Thus, by Schaefer’s fixed point theorem [11], \mathcal{H} has a fixed point which is a solution of problem (2). \square

5. Existence Results for the Third Problem

Definition 5.1. A solution of (3) is a function $\chi \in C([-\kappa, \varpi], \mathbb{R})$ where

$$\chi(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^{\varpi} e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)} (\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^{\theta} e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)} (\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)} \Phi(\lambda) d\lambda, & \theta \in [0, \varpi], \\ \wp(\theta), & \theta \in [-\kappa, 0], \end{cases}$$

where $\Phi \in C(\Theta)$, with $\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_{\rho(\theta, \chi_{\theta})}, \Phi(\theta))$.

The hypotheses:

- (H₃) The function Ψ verifies:

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) - \Psi(\theta, \chi_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)| \leq \omega_3\|\chi_1 - \chi_2\|_{[-\kappa, 0]} + \omega_4|\mathfrak{S}_1 - \mathfrak{S}_2|,$$

for any $\chi_1, \mathfrak{S}_1 \in C([-\kappa, 0], \mathbb{R})$, $\chi_2, \mathfrak{S}_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, and each $\theta \in \Theta$, where $\omega_3 > 0$, $0 < \omega_4 < 1$.

Remark 5.2. We note that by taking:

$$A_1 = \omega_3, \quad A_2 = \omega_4, \quad \text{and } A_3 = \Psi^*,$$

where $\Psi^* = \sup_{\theta \in [0, \varpi]} \Psi(\theta, 0, 0)$. Then, hypothesis (H₃) implies that

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S})| \leq A_1\|\chi\|_{[-\kappa, 0]} + A_2|\mathfrak{S}| + A_3,$$

for any $\chi \in C([-\kappa, 0], \mathbb{R})$, $v \in \mathfrak{S}$, and each $\theta \in \Theta$.

As in Theorems 3.3 and 3.4, we obtain the following.

Theorem 5.3. *If (H_3) holds and*

$$\frac{\varpi^\zeta(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)\omega_3}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - \omega_4)} < 1,$$

then (3) admit a unique solution on $[-\kappa, \varpi]$.

Theorem 5.4. *If (H_3) is verified and*

$$\frac{\varpi^\zeta(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)A_1}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - A_2)} < 1,$$

then (3) admit at least one solution on $[-\kappa, \varpi]$.

6. The Existence Results for the Fourth Problem

Definition 6.1. *A solution of (4) is a function $\chi \in \Xi$ where*

$$\chi(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{\varrho e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j} - \frac{j e^{-\varepsilon\theta}}{\Gamma(\zeta)(\imath e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)} \int_0^\varpi e^{-\varepsilon(\varpi-\lambda)}(\varpi - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)}\Phi(\lambda)d\lambda \\ + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\zeta)} \int_0^\theta e^{-\varepsilon(\theta-\lambda)}(\theta - \lambda)^{(\zeta-1)}\Phi(\lambda)d\lambda, \theta \in [0, \varpi], \\ \wp(\theta), \theta \in [-\infty, 0], \end{cases}$$

where $\Phi \in C(\Theta)$, with $\Phi(\theta) = \Psi(\theta, \chi_{\rho(\theta, \chi_\theta)}, \Phi(\theta))$.

Set

$$\delta' := \delta'_{\rho^-} = \{\rho(\theta, \chi) : \theta \in \Theta, \chi \in \mathcal{G} \rho(\theta, \chi) < 0\}.$$

Suppose that $\rho : \Theta \times \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous and $\theta \rightarrow \chi_\theta$ is continuous from δ' into \mathcal{G} . (H_η) There exists a continuous bounded function $\varrho : \delta'_{\rho^-} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ where

$$\|\eta_\theta\|_{\mathcal{G}} \leq \varrho(\theta)\|\eta\|_{\mathcal{G}}, \text{ for any } \theta \in \delta'.$$

Lemma 6.2. *If $\chi \in \Xi$ then*

$$\|\chi_\theta\|_{\mathcal{G}} = (\xi_2 + \varpi')\|\eta\|_{\mathcal{G}} + \xi_1 \sup_{\lambda \in [0, \max\{0, \theta\}]} \|\chi(\lambda)\|,$$

where

$$\varpi' = \sup_{\theta \in \delta'} \varpi(\theta).$$

The hypothesis:

- (H_5) The function Ψ verifies:

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) - \Psi(\theta, \chi_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)| \leq b_3\|\chi_1 - \chi_2\|_{\mathcal{G}} + b_4|\mathfrak{S}_1 - \mathfrak{S}_2|,$$

for any $\chi_1, \mathfrak{S}_1 \in \mathcal{G}$, $\chi_2, \mathfrak{S}_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, and each $\theta \in \Theta$, where $b_3 > 0$ and $0 < b_4 < 1$.

Remark 6.3. *We note that by taking:*

$$B_4 = b_3, \quad B_5 = b_4, \text{ and } B_6 = \Psi^*,$$

where $\Psi^* = \sup_{\theta \in [0, \varpi]} \Psi(\theta, 0, 0)$. Then, hypothesis (H_5) implies that

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S})| \leq B_4\|\chi\|_{\mathcal{G}} + B_5|\mathfrak{S}| + B_6,$$

for any $\chi \in \mathcal{G}$, $\mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{R}$, and each $\theta \in \Theta$.

As in Theorems 4.3 and 4.4, we have the following.

Theorem 6.4. *If (H_5) holds and*

$$\frac{\varpi^\zeta(\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)b_3}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - b_4)} < 1,$$

then (4) admit a unique solution on $(-\infty, \varpi]$.

Theorem 6.5. *If (H_φ) and (H_5) are met, then (4) admit at least one solution on $(-\infty, \varpi]$.*

7. Some Examples

We give now some examples that illustrate our obtained results throughout the paper.

Example 7.1. *Consider the following problem:*

$$\begin{cases} \left({}^C_0\mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\frac{1}{2},1}\chi \right) (\theta) = \frac{1}{90(1 + \|\chi_\theta\|)} + \frac{1}{30\left(1 + \left| \left({}^C_0\mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\frac{1}{2},1}\chi \right) (\theta) \right| \right)}; \theta \in [0, 1], \\ \chi(0) + \chi(1) = 0, \\ \chi(\theta) = 1 + \theta^2; \theta \in [-1, 0]. \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

Set

$$\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S}) = \frac{1}{90(1 + \|\chi\|)} + \frac{1}{30(1 + |\mathfrak{S}|)}; \theta \in [0, 1], \chi \in \mathcal{C}, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{R}.$$

For any $\chi, \tilde{\chi} \in \mathcal{C}$, $\chi, \tilde{\chi} \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\theta \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S}) - \Psi(\theta, \tilde{\chi}, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}})| \leq \frac{1}{90}\|\chi - \tilde{\chi}\|_{[-1,0]} + \frac{1}{30}|\mathfrak{S} - \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}|.$$

Hence hypothesis (H_1) is satisfied with

$$\omega_1 = \frac{1}{90} \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_2 = \frac{1}{30}.$$

Next, condition (9) is verifies with $\varepsilon = 1$ and $r = \frac{1}{2}$. Indeed,

$$\frac{\varpi^\zeta(\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + 2j)b_3}{\Gamma(\zeta + 1)(\varrho e^{\varepsilon\varpi} + j)(1 - b_4)} = \frac{(e + 2)\frac{1}{90}}{(e + 1)\left(1 - \frac{1}{30}\right)\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} < 1.$$

Some calculations indicate that all of the requirements of Theorem 3.3 are verified. Thus, (16) has a unique solution.

Example 7.2. *Consider the following example:*

$$\begin{cases} \left({}^C_0\mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\frac{1}{2},1}\chi \right) (\theta) = \frac{\chi_\theta e^{-\gamma\theta+\theta}}{180(e^\theta - e^{-\theta})(1 + \|\chi_\theta\|)} + \frac{\chi(\theta)e^{-\gamma\theta+\theta}}{60(e^\theta - e^{-\theta})\left(1 + \left| \left({}^C_0\mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\frac{1}{2},1}\chi \right) (\theta) \right| \right)}; \theta \in [0, 1], \\ \chi(0) + \chi(1) = 0, \\ \chi(\theta) = \theta + 1; \theta \in (-\infty, 0]. \end{cases} \tag{17}$$

Let γ be a positive real constant and

$$B_\gamma = \{\chi \in C((-\infty, 1], \mathbb{R},) : \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow -\infty} e^{\gamma\lambda}\chi(\lambda) \text{ exists in } \mathbb{R}\}. \tag{18}$$

The norm of B_γ is given by

$$\|\chi\|_\gamma = \sup_{\lambda \in (-\infty, 1]} e^{\gamma\lambda} |\chi(\lambda)|.$$

Let $\chi : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be such that $\chi_0 \in B_\gamma$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow -\infty} e^{\gamma\lambda} \chi_\theta(\lambda) &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow -\infty} e^{\gamma\lambda} \chi(\theta + \lambda - 1) = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow -\infty} e^{\gamma(\lambda - \theta + 1)} \chi(\lambda) \\ &= e^{\gamma(-\theta + 1)} \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow -\infty} e^{\gamma\lambda} \chi_1(\lambda) < \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\chi_\theta \in B_\gamma$. Finally we prove that

$$\|\chi_\theta\|_\gamma \leq \xi_1 \|\chi_1\|_\gamma + \xi_2 \sup_{\vartheta \in [0, \theta]} |\chi(\vartheta)|,$$

where $\xi_1 = \xi_2 = 1$ and $\xi_3 = 1$. We have

$$\|\chi_\theta(\lambda)\| = |\chi(\theta + \lambda)|.$$

If $\theta + \lambda \leq 1$, we get

$$\|\chi_\theta(\xi)\| \leq \sup_{\vartheta \in (-\infty, 0]} |\chi(\vartheta)|.$$

For $\theta + \lambda \geq 0$, then we have

$$\|\chi_\theta(\xi)\| \leq \sup_{\vartheta \in [0, \theta]} |\chi(\vartheta)|.$$

Thus for all $\theta + \lambda \in \Theta$, we get

$$\|\chi_\theta(\xi)\| \leq \sup_{\vartheta \in (-\infty, 0]} |\chi(\vartheta)| + \sup_{\vartheta \in [0, \theta]} |\chi(\vartheta)|.$$

Then

$$\|\chi_\theta\|_\gamma \leq \|\chi_0\|_\gamma + \sup_{\vartheta \in [0, \theta]} |\chi(\vartheta)|.$$

It is clear that $(B_\gamma, \|\cdot\|)$ is a Banach space. We can conclude that B_γ a phase space.

Set

$$\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S}) = \frac{e^{-\gamma\theta + \theta}}{180(e^\theta - e^{-\theta})(1 + \|\chi\|_{B_\gamma})} + \frac{e^{-\gamma\theta + \theta}}{60(e^\theta - e^{-\theta})(1 + |\mathfrak{S}|)}; \theta \in [0, 1], \chi \in B_\gamma, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{R}.$$

For any $\chi, \tilde{\chi} \in B_\gamma$, $\mathfrak{S}, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}} \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\theta \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S}) - \Psi(\theta, \tilde{\chi}, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}})| \leq \frac{1}{180} \|\chi - \tilde{\chi}\|_{B_\gamma} + \frac{1}{60} |\mathfrak{S} - \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}|.$$

Hence hypothesis (H_2) is satisfied with

$$b_1 = \frac{1}{180} \quad \text{and} \quad b_2 = \frac{1}{60}.$$

All requirements of Theorem 4.4 are met. Then, problem (17) has at least one solution defined on $(-\infty, 1]$.

Example 7.3. We consider the following problem

$$\begin{cases} \left(\left({}^C_0 \mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\frac{1}{2}, 1} \chi \right) (\theta) = \frac{1}{90(1 + |\chi(\theta - \sigma(\chi(\theta)))|)} + \frac{1}{30 \left(1 + \left| \left({}^C_0 \mathfrak{D}_\theta^{\frac{1}{2}, 1} \chi \right) (\theta) \right| \right)}; \theta \in [0, 1], \right. \\ \chi(0) + \chi(1) = 0, \\ \left. \chi(\theta) = 1 + \theta^2; \theta \in [-1, 0]. \right. \end{cases} \tag{19}$$

where $\sigma \in C(\mathbb{R}, [0, 1])$. Set

$$\rho(\theta, \wp) = \theta - \sigma(\wp(0)), \quad (\theta, \wp) \in [0, 1] \times C([-1, 0], \mathbb{R}),$$

$$\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S}) = \frac{1}{90(1 + |\chi(\theta - \sigma(\chi(\theta)))|)} + \frac{1}{30(1 + |\mathfrak{S}(\theta)|)}; \quad \theta \in [0, 1], \chi \in \mathcal{C}, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{R}.$$

For $\chi, \tilde{\chi} \in \mathcal{C}$, $\mathfrak{S}, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}} \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\theta \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$|\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S}) - \Psi(\theta, \tilde{\chi}, \tilde{\mathfrak{S}})| \leq \frac{1}{90} \|\chi - \tilde{\chi}\|_{[-1, 0]} + \frac{1}{30} |\mathfrak{S} - \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}|.$$

Hence hypothesis (H_3) is satisfied with

$$\omega_3 = \frac{1}{90} \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_4 = \frac{1}{30}.$$

All requirements of Theorem 5.3 are verified. Thus, (19) has a unique solution defined on $[-1, 1]$.

Example 7.4. Consider now the problem:

$$\begin{cases} \left({}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\frac{1}{2}, 1} \chi \right) (\theta) = \frac{\chi(\theta - \varepsilon(\chi(\theta)))e^{-\gamma\theta + \theta}}{180(e^\theta - e^{-\theta})(1 + |\chi(\theta - \sigma(\chi(\theta)))|)} + \frac{\chi(\theta)e^{-\gamma\theta + \theta}}{60(e^\theta - e^{-\theta}) \left(1 + \left| \left({}^C \mathfrak{D}_{\theta}^{\frac{1}{2}, 1} \chi \right) (\theta) \right| \right)}; \quad \theta \in [0, 2], \\ \chi(0) + \chi(1) = 0, \\ \chi(\theta) = \theta; \quad \theta \in (-\infty, 0]. \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Define

$$\rho(\theta, \wp) = \theta - \varepsilon(\wp(0)), \quad (\theta, \wp) \in [0, 2] \times B_\gamma,$$

and set

$$\Psi(\theta, \chi, \mathfrak{S}) = \frac{e^{-\gamma\theta + \theta}}{180(e^\theta - e^{-\theta})(1 + \|\chi\|_{B_\gamma})} + \frac{e^{-\gamma\theta + \theta}}{60(e^\theta - e^{-\theta})(1 + |\mathfrak{S}|)},$$

where $\theta \in [0, 2]$, $\chi \in B_\gamma$, $\mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{R}$. We can demonstrate that all conditions of Theorem 4.4 are verified. Then, (20) has at least one solution defined on $(-\infty, 2]$.

Declarations

Ethical approval This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors.

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